

CONTINUITY OF TRADITIONS AND CREATION OF THE AUTHOR'S METHODS FOR TRAINING VOCALISTS: FROM THE PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE OF K.A. AKDAULETOVA***Tolepbergen A.***

*Master of Arts in Art History,
lecturer at the Vocal Art Department
Kurmangazy Kazakh National Conservatory
Almaty, Kazakhstan
ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-4051-2844>*

Yusupova A.

*MBA, Associate Professor Kurmangazy
Kazakh National Conservatory
Almaty, Kazakhstan
ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6246-7106>*

Abstract

Karakoz Akdauletova was one of the first students of Bibigul Akhmetovna Tulegenova, the People's Artist of the USSR and Kazakhstan, Hero of Socialist Labor, Winner of State Prizes of the USSR and Kazakhstan, scholar. After graduating from the Conservatoire, she was actively engaged in concert performance and teaching at the Kazangap Kyzylorda Music School, where she served as head of the vocal department. From that time, laying the foundation for vocal education, K.A. Akdauletova began to develop a classical vocal school in the region. The results of her work proved highly successful; her students became laureates of national and international vocal competitions. Among her students are well-known performers of Kazakh pop and opera, including Madina Saduakasova, Nabi Aimuratov, Almas Kishkenbayev, Kuralay Meyrambek, Bibigul Zhanuzak, Maksat Makulbekov, Samal Bayseitova and others.

On December 9, 1996, Karakoz Akdauletova was awarded the title "Honored Artist of the Republic of Kazakhstan"; on November 29, 2019, she was received the Order of Kurmet.

Keywords: vocal pedagogy, performing skills, author's methodology, music education, vocal school, vocal training.

Introduction

Vocal art is one of the most expressive forms of art, which has a rich history, from the ancient times to present. Initially, it served as means of communication and expression of emotions, but gradually, having become independent, it gained enormous popularity. Singers began to work on improving their singing and acting skills, as vocal art is not only beautiful singing, but also the ability to convey emotions through music, thus uniting people of different cultures and nationalities.

The vocal art of Kazakhstan is considered to be one of the youngest, as it developed in the last century. However, during this relatively short period, it has managed to unite different eras, connecting the past and present of our country.

Both opera and chamber music performers have increasingly shown interest in the development of domestic vocal art in its various genres and trends, in the context of issues problems of musical performance and creativity of outstanding musicians.

Turning to primary sources and foundational principles, young talents try to grasp the secrets of the performing skills of renowned singers and to study the pedagogical methods of their mentors.

A special place among talented performers and teachers is occupied by K.A. Akdauletova (1956-2021), Honored Artist of the Republic of Kazakhstan, who made a significant contribution to the Kazakh musical culture, to the development of classical vocal art in the Kyzylorda region, and trained many talented opera and pop performers.

In this context, the pedagogical experience of K.A. Akdauletova is of particular scientific interest as it reflects both individual practice and the formation of regional vocal school. The scientific novelty of this study lies in the systematization of her authorial vocal methodology and in identifying its role in the development of professional vocal training in Kazakhstan. The practical significance of the research is determined by the possibility of applying these pedagogical principles in modern vocal pedagogy and educational practice.

Karakoz Akzhigitovna Akdauletova dedicated her life to the art of singing. She was born on March 3, 1956 in the village of Airkol, Syrdarya district, Kyzylorda region. From childhood, she loved to singing, performed at various events, and participated in competitions. At one of these competitions, she attracted the attention of the Kyzylorda, composer Mulkaman Kalauov. After graduating from school, she entered the N.V. Gogol Pedagogical Institute.

Later in 1979, her performance with the song and dance ensemble "Syr Suluy", organized at the Kyzylorda Regional House of Folk Art, was noticed by Baigali Dosymzhanov (soloist at the Abai State Academic Opera and Ballet Theater and teacher at the Kurmangazy State Conservatoire), who was invited her to participate in this concert. Upon his recommendation, in 1980 K. Akdauletova entered the Kurmangazy State Conservatoire in Almaty to study under Professor Bibigul Tulegenova, People's Artist of the USSR. According to B.A. Tulegenova: "Karakoz is my first, closest, curious, honest and talented student. She graduated

from the pedagogical university and immediately entered the second year of the Conservatoire. She had a beautiful, clear and resonant voice.”

After graduating from the Conservatoire Karakoz performed extensively in concert activities. Her repertoire included arias and chamber works by foreign, Russian and Kazakh composers, as well as folk songs. She possessed a lyric-coloratura soprano voice and remarkable natural technique. Her voice is distinguished by a pure and clear timbre, lightness, and good vocal projection. Karakoz Akdauletova was known as “The Nightingale of the Kyzylorda Land.”

As B.A. Tulegenova recalls: “When I went to Kyzylorda with my concerts, I always included Karakoz in the program. I often thought that she should have stayed in Almaty, sung in the Opera Theater and taught at the Conservatoire. But then I realized that she had made the right choice; as a student, she said she would return to her home city and develop vocal art in Kyzylorda. And she fulfilled her mission. Karakoz became not only a singer and teacher, but also a public figure who contributed greatly to the cultural sphere of Kyzylorda. She received numerous titles and the love of the people. For her hard work and dedication to her profession, she was awarded the title of Honored Artist of the Republic of Kazakhstan. This became a great joy and pride for me - my first student achieved such success!”

K.A. Akdauletova combined concert performance and teaching activities. Her students include winners of various Republican and International competitions, as well as recipients of honorary titles of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

As a student, K. Akdauletova kept a diary which she recorded exercises, comments, and recommendations from her vocal coach. Carefully preserving her teacher's instructions, she later became a teacher herself and founded the classical vocal school of the Kyzylorda region. In her teaching activities, K.A. Akdauletova adhered to the basic principles of vocal pedagogy. She considered the most important principles to be gradual and consistent training, as well as the principle of unity between technical and artistic aspects.

It should be emphasized that these principles correspond to the general trends of classical vocal pedagogy; however, in Akdauletova's practice they acquire a regionally specific character. This adaptation is reflected in the combination of academic vocal training with elements of national musical traditions, as well as in a flexible approach to the individual vocal development of students. K. Akdauletova began the professional development of her students from the age of five, introducing children to vocal performance practice through participation in concerts and children's competitions. Upon reaching the age of 13-14, based on their acquired skills and abilities, as well as the vocal potential (range, vocal fullness, etc.), she divided students into two categories - popular and academic singing.

Such differentiation can be considered a pedagogically justified, as it allows for the early professional orientation of students. In contrast to unified training models, this approach contributes to a more targeted development of vocal technique and stylistics thinking,

taking into account the physiological and artistic characteristics of the performer.

The development of vocal and performance culture, as well as repertoire selection, was carried out taking into account vocal development, musical abilities, and the psychological characteristics of student.

She considered careful repertoire selection to be one of the key issues in vocal pedagogy, as it contributes to the development of basic vocal technical skills as well as musical and artistic taste of students. From a methodological perspective, repertoire selection serves not only as a pedagogical tool but also as a mechanism for shaping artistic thinking. In this regard, Akdauletova's approach demonstrates a balance between technical complexity and expressive content, which ensures the gradual development of both vocal skills and interpretative competence.

The introduction to a musical piece usually began with a short digression: she briefly spoke about the historical period, the composer's work, the stylistic features of the author's writing, and the character of the piece. In her opinion, this information was essential for broadening the performer's vision and ensuring deeper immersion into a musical work and, as a result, its accurate interpretation. The analysis of the selected musical piece included its form, texture, tessitura, vocal and technical difficulties, phrase structure, and culmination. Methodological approaches to students were aimed at developing vocal technique, clear intonation, precise and expressive diction, proper breath control, dynamics, and vocal register blending.

K.A. Akdauletova paid special attention to vocal production and the development of vocal technique, focusing on the characteristics. She selected exercises aimed at developing specific aspects of the vocal apparatus. For example, given the weakness of the articulatory apparatus, she worked on diction and clear pronunciation both in exercises and in musical pieces. When learning lyrics, consonant were deliberately emphasized, while vowels in combination with consonants were carefully prolonged. Expressive reading of poetic text was considered essential.

From her first lessons, she emphasized properly organized singing breathing and vocal onset. Karakoz Akdauletova aimed at achieve softness and, at the same time, clarity of vocal production, without unnecessary breathy onsets. The lesson began with special breathing exercises using consonant such as “TS”, “F”, followed by calm and controlled breathing on “ma-me-mi-mo-mu”. After that, she moved on to an exercise for activating head resonator (singing the “M” sound with the closed mouth).

An exercise in vowel alignment in combination with consonants was considered essential, for example: da-de-di-do-du, za-ze-zi-zo-zu, etc.

In her warm-ups, K.A. Akdauletova often used staccato. According to the teacher, this technique contributes to the development of a firm vocal onset, lightness of the voice, and increased breath control. Exercise for developing dynamics and maintaining a high position during a descending phrases were performed alternating between forte and piano, staccato and legato.

When performing exercises for vocal register blending, strengthen breathing abilities, and developing vocal flexibility, K.A. Akdauletova recommended singing with the vowels "a" and "ya", or in combination

with the consonant patters such "za" and "mi-ya-mi", etc.

Based on the author's methodology, it can be concluded that in developing a system of professional vocal qualities, Akdauletova applied an individual approach to each student based on students' natural vocal and performing abilities, as well as on their individuality and creativity.

The system of exercises used by Akdauletova reflects a structured approach to voice formation, where each technical element is consistently developed. Such a sequence corresponds to the principles of systematic vocal training and ensures stability and flexibility of vocal performance.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the systematic reconstruction of the authorial vocal-pedagogical methodology of K.A. Akdauletova, which has not previously been described in academic literature as an integrated system. The study identifies and structures the key components of her pedagogical approach, including the principles of early professional orientation, differentiated vocal training, and repertoire-based artistic development.

In addition, the research clarifies the role of technical vocal exercises in her teaching system and demonstrates how they contribute to the formation of both vocal technique and interpretative thinking.

As a result, an integrated model of regional vocal pedagogy is formulated reflected, the synthesis of classical academic training and individualized teaching strategies.

Methods. The methodological approach of this study is based on integration of two dimensions (historical and methodological) within the biographical framework of the material, highlighting the traditions of the development of Kazakh vocal art. This approach allowed the study to address the foundations of the vocal pedagogical process, teaching methodology, and practical implementation, based on A.K. Akdauletova's long-term pedagogical experience.

The pedagogical principles are presented from the general to the specific. Specific techniques of her vocal pedagogical methodology are also described. The influence of this pedagogical practice on the artistic, pedagogical and performing activities of her followers is also considered.

Discussion. The analysis of Akdauletova's pedagogical system shows that her methodology integrates traditional principles of classical vocal training with an individualized approach. Unlike standardized teaching models, her method places particular emphasis on artistic imagination and interpretative thinking, which are

considered essential components of professional vocal performance.

The main task set by K.A. Akdauletova for her students was not only the development of vocal and technical abilities, but also competent reading of the author's text, accurate interpretation and stylistic rendering of the of the musical work, as well as artistic expressiveness.

According to I.V. Vilinskaya, "The logic of musical thought is the art of phrasing. The correct use of musical techniques - staccato, legato, semantic highlighting of musical phrases, articulation and breathing - all these are the most important means of musical expressiveness and creation an artistic image" [1].

A.L. Dolivo in his book *"The Singer and the Song"* noted that "singing is similar to the expressiveness of human speech because "singing is a kind of human speech, clothed in especially expressive musical intonations," notes [12, 9].

Throughout the entire period of training, K.A. Akdauletova paid attention to the development of imagination. She emphasized that singers should have creative imagination, since, in revealing the content of the work, the singer creates a new artistic image, which also develops through other musical abilities (rhythm, intonation, performance expressiveness, etc.).

The human voice is the most natural and most complex musical instrument; it can acquire vitality, gaining flexibility and poetic expressiveness, or it can become weak, dull, and uninteresting. Vocal sound characteristics are closely associated with emotions. Sound may be "bright", "projected" and "light", etc. Imagery in vocal sound is associated with vivid emotional representations. No musical exercise or learned phrase should be performed without imagination, fantasy, and emotional coloring. Mechanical and unreflective repetition of material does not contribute to artistic development and lacks expressiveness. Every musical thought its own logic (motive, phrase, sentence and period) [13].

Having extensive concert and performing experience, Karakoz Akdauletova often shared her feelings, skills of "control" over herself and internal emotions, as well as methods of overcoming stage anxiety. She found the right words for each student and gave clear instructions before going on stage.

V.Yu. Grigoriev writes in his book: "A concert performance becomes a "litmus test" for the performer, because here the performer is required to rise above the ordinary level of craftsmanship and become a true artist,

opening the path to creativity for listeners and demonstrating a high level which of artistic mastery.” [11].

Having extensive concert and performing experience, Karakoz Akdauletova often shared her

Experience of self-control and emotional regulation, as well as methods for overcoming stage anxiety. She was able to find appropriate words for each student and provided clear instruction before going on stage. From a pedagogical perspective, it is understood that a concert performer should be developed gradually through consistent improvement performing skills, while progressively expanding professional and artistic horizons towards which the performer should strive [14].

Thus, Akdauletova`s pedagogical approach can be viewed not only as a set of practical techniques but also as a holistic system aimed at the formation of the artistic identity of the performer.

Results: In the course of this study, the stages of K.A. Akdauletova`s the life and creative development were identified. Practical teaching principles and methods were systematized, and set of exercises used for vocal formation and development was analyzed. These finding made it possible to outline the main features of her authorial methodology and to establish a connection between of K.A.Akdauletova's performing activity and her role in the development of vocal art in the region and the country. In addition, the study examined her personal and professional contacts with Bibigul Akhmetovna Tulegenova, People`s Artist of the USSR and Kazakhstan.

Conclusion: The finding of this study may be useful for examining the history of the development of domestic vocal art and processes of forming regional vocal schools, as well as for understanding the professional development of singer-performer and musician-teachers. They may

also used to define the theoretical, historical and methodological content of courses in vocal art and vocal pedagogy.

The results of the study confirm that the authorial methodology of K.A.Akdauletova represents a significant stage in the development of Kazakh vocal pedagogy. Its distinctive feature lies in the synthesis of classical vocal traditions and individual pedagogical strategies, which ensures its relevance in contemporary music education.

References

1. Vilinskaya I.N. The importance of the repertoire in the education of a singer // *Questions of Vocal Pedagogy*. Vol. 3. Moscow, 1967. pp.45-91;
2. Derjzhny V.A. On the principles and methods of Soviet vocal pedagogy // *Questions of Vocal Pedagogy*. Vol. 3. Moscow, 1967. pp.5-45.
3. Yusupova A.A. Development of a singer`s performing culture in the process of vocal training // *Problems of Musical Performance and Education*. Moscow, 2018. pp.79-84.
4. Melani M. Parliamo un po`di canto [Let`s talk a little about singing]. Almaty: Format, 2003. 120 p.
5. Bagadurov V.A. *Essays on the History of Vocal Pedagogy*. Part 2. Saint Petersburg: Lan`, 2020. 476 p.
6. Sydykova R., Yussupova A., Berekeshev G., Smailova T., Kuldinov N. Vocal pedagogy and performance studies // *Life Science Global*, 2020, Vol. 8, No. 3. Available at: <https://www.lifescienceglobal.com/pms/index.php/jiddt/article/view/6799> (accessed: 2026). (Indexed in Scopus, Author ID: 57190584644).
7. Sydykova R., Narbekova B., Kakimova L., To-bagabylova A, Esdauletova K., Yelzhanov D. Musical performance interpretation in Kazakh art education // *Opción*, 2020, Vol. 36, Special Issue 26, pp. 57–75. Available at: <https://produccioncientificaluz.org/index.php/opcion/article/view/31702>
8. Interview with B.A. Tulegenova. Documentary interview, November 2023. (Video source).
9. Sydykova R.Sh., Yusupova A.A., Kakimova L.Sh., Yesdauletova K.A., Ethnocultural aspects of musical performance in Kazakhstan in the context of the state program “Tugan El”. Shymkent, 2020. 72 p.
10. Yusupova A.A., Sarkytbay Zh.. General trends in the development of the chamber-vocal genre//*Proceeding of the round table dedicated B. Zhilisbaev*/. Almaty, 2023. pp. 70-74
11. Grigoryev V. Yu., *A Performer and Stage Performance*. Moscow-Magnitogorsk, 1988. 75 p.
12. Dolivo A.L., *A Singer and a Song*. Moscow: Muzgiz, 1948. 250 p.
13. *Questions of Vocal Pedagogy*. Vol. 3. Moscow: Music, 1967. 146 p.
14. Dragun O.G., *Stage Anxiety and Methods of Overcoming It*. Saratov, 2018. 18 p.